

The Nature of the Homelands in South Africa

Nomonde Nelisiwe Jele

Department of Historical Studies (Howard Campus), School of Arts, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban, South Africa

Homelands became one of the most effective political modus operandi to divide and rule Blacks in South Africa. It became another effective form of alienating Blacks from the South African mainstream economy and politics, as they had to be placed in ethnically divided areas where the main human necessity was very scarce. The Group Areas Act of 1950 became the divisive Act that separated Whites from Blacks, but the Homelands Act of 1959 became a divisive Act between Blacks and Blacks as it put more emphasis on the separation of black people. This Act of Homelands became the Act that encourages competition among Blacks instead of unifying them for the common good. Blacks under Homelands had to develop as individual ethnic groups that would set their goals without including others. In this way became easy for the apartheid government to deal with individual black ethnic group than unified groups. Homelands in this way became a divisive mechanism that left Blacks in less productive and non-arable land, system that would keep them fully dependent on white people for their livelihood.

Keywords: Modus operandi, homelands, less-productive and non-arable, the group areas act of 1950

The Homelands system ran through three presidential eras that were Hendriek Verwoerd, John Vorster and Botha, something that showed its political magnitude. Verwoerd, as initiator, did very little as he was limited by his untimely death in 1966. The rest of its operation on Vorster Botha as it was under them that this system came into fruition. The main objective for Homelands was to alienate Blacks from all South African state resources by giving them a pseudo-independence that had no international recognition. The homelands, as the institute for a foundation of pseudo-independence were founded on the ethnic separate development, for the black people to be suspicious of one another as something that confirmed the policy of divide and rule. Therefore, fore means that homelands were for the black ethnic intolerance so that their development could remain unequalled.

Above anything else, homelands were about keeping Blacks nowhere near Whites in any form of socio-economic development. Blacks are naturally soil-dependent, but as things were, the most arable land had been taken from them through various means, such as land usurpation that was done by means of different Acts, and land dependence became totally impossible. Economically, Blacks had to work under the homelands; Blacks had to sell their labour either to mines or on farms to make ends meet. Educational lacks had to be allocated only to ethnically designed institutions, something that meant that Sesotho-speaking students had to attend local educational institutions just like other black ethnic groups. The point was that under homelands-Blacks had to be without foreign influence other than the ethnic one to avoid ethnic diversity. Shortly, these are things

that homelands intended to achieve.

The Nature of the Homelands in South Africa

The homelands technically started during Johannes Strydom, who was so inclined in the racial separation in South Africa, his early death gave him no time to implement it. Dr Hendrik Verwoerd, who was his successor and an ardent advocate of racial separation, in 1959 came with an Act that became known as the Promotion of Bantu Self-Government Act of 1959 that confirmed the proposal of these homelands. The Promotion of Bantu Self-Government Act of 1959 directly intended to create the enclave black ethnic groups in their respective homelands. They were at first set up into eight and later were taken up to ten, and they were known as Bantu Homelands. Places like Kwa-Zulu, under Mangosuthu Buthelezi was reluctant to accept the so-called independence, as he preferred to be referred KwaZulu to as a Self-governing state rather than an independent state.

Mangosuthu Gatsha Buthelezi, a pivotal figure in South Africa's history, refused to accept the illusion of apartheid's "independence" for KwaZulu Bantustan, challenging the National Party government.¹

The fact was that, despite Chief Buthelezi's reluctance, the strategy of setting homelands system was never disturbed at all. The main aim of these homelands was to fully separate Black ethnic groups from one another, and secondly, it purported to alienate the black people from the central economic dispensation of South Africa. Thirdly, it wanted to deurbanize the rightless African people, something that led to African townships being removed from the control of white municipalities and being controlled by the Bantu Affairs Administration Boards (BAABS). This, in short, led to the creation of nine pseudo-states that were only recognized South African entities since they all, one by one, lacked international recognition.

Over and above anything else, homelands intended to create a separate development between Whites and Blacks, something that would establish and promote white supremacy in South Africa, as

Author Note

Nomonde Nelisiwe Jele, Department of Historical Studies (Howard Campus), School of Arts, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban South Africa

I have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Nomonde Nelisiwe Jele, Department of Historical Studies (Howard Campus), School of Arts, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban South Africa

E-mail: mondehjele@gmail.com

¹Kenny, *Mangosuthu Buthelezi: A Complex Legacy in the Struggle Against Apartheid*-BIZNEWS, 1.

Verwoerd once stressed: We want to make South Africa white...keeping it white can mean only one thing, namely domination, not leadership, not guidance, but control, supremacy². This, of course, was about the promotion of South African political philosophy that meant keeping Blacks under perpetual white control. Homelands in this way became an imported idea from European countries that are predominantly white, but forgetting one thing that Africa is a black-owned continent where black people could not be shifted away. Homelands, in broader terms, meant the meanness of resources that had been directed to Blacks since black farmers in homelands remained hugely unsubsidized, unlike white farmers in the South African mainstream.

In the black homelands, agricultural production was primarily in subsistence farming. Whereas mechanisation advanced the levels of commercial agriculture for white farmers, black farmers did not receive the same subsidies³.

This was the true characteristic of separate development that had to be projected by the creation of homelands where Blacks had to fend for themselves, while Whites were given what they needed, financial backing for their own development. Furthermore, homelands proved to be more about the black deprivation of resources that they had to have access to. In the first place, the big portion of land that had resources in South African soil was politically taken away from Blacks through the land usurpation of the Land Act 1913 and other similar Acts that followed. The black homelands, which were spread throughout South Africa, comprised only 13% of the country's surface area, and the mineral riches, industries and most fertile agricultural land for the most part remained in white possession⁴. There were several instances of dispossession that people like black women suffered under the homeland related laws such as the Bantu Laws Amendments Act that forbade African women from visiting their partners in urban areas. The 1964 Bantu Laws Amendment Act prohibited African women from entering urban areas, except with a visitors permit⁵. Homelands in this way-clearly put the separate development into practice, where Whites surpass Blacks in every aspect life.

In a broader sphere of homelands, Blacks would be contained in homeland where they would enjoy their restricted citizenship, as they were going to lose -South African citizenship. Black people would eventually gain citizenship of their respective homelands and would thereby lose their South African citizenship, and their rights lose their South African citizenship in the designated areas⁶. This was a true betrayal of the black South African political interests in the country which they had a natural entitlement to it. This whole state of affairs led black people to the state of being eco-politically manipulated, as the enclave of white people, like farmers, made a protest through the *Elandslaagte* Farmers Association in Northern Natal by stating this:

The Native are not farmers and never will be farmers. He would ruin every bit of land that was placed at his disposal, and it was the height of folly and irresponsibility to hand the district to Natives⁷.

Naturally, Blacks are so soil-dependent-in this way, soil was and still is the major source of self-sustenance. This therefore means that anything that impedes them from using the land in a rewarding manner, their life sustenance could be brought into jeopardy. White farmers had claimed that they fought against the success of black farmers in homelands because any success of black farmers could cut the labour supply from the homelands. Paradoxically, all the

homelands that had gone for independence were economically less viable so, something that made them labour reservoirs either in mines or on farms.

The homelands that legally became 'independent' in terms of this policy-Transkei, Bophuthatswana, Venda and Ciskei- literally had it thrust upon them by the white government, with the collaboration of certain chiefs and puppet bureaucracy. None of the homelands -was economically viable. They were, in effect, labour reserves for the mining and agriculture industry⁸.

In this way, homelands became a pool that was inhabited by the different species of contrasting fortunes, as the leaders with their closest cohorts were in the economic comfort zone' while people on the ground were languishing in dire poverty. Homelands, despite their common goal of black independence, had no collective intention to either promote or advance the economic sphere of the people, the very reason they remained unconnected enclaves. It is noteworthy to say that Verwoerd's tragic and untimely death in 1966 cut short his intention of seeing the establishment of this hideous act of racial separation in the form of homelands.

These homelands were generally fragmented, particularly as the consolidation plans that were put forward in the 1950s had been rejected under the pressure from the farmers who would have lost their land, and in recognition of the primacy of white interests; all apartheid rhetoric notwithstanding, that KwaZulu consisted of eleven separate patches of territories and Bophuthatswana seven⁹.

It was for this reason that under homelands structures, Africans had to develop themselves along ethnic lines, something that purely formed a divide and rule system as it was intended by the apartheid government after its victory in 1948. Homelands were then used as an instrument for ethnic division, something that was totally against the black ethnic unity, as it promoted and propounded ethnic individuality of the worst kind. These homeland institutions created a huge debate among their leaders as some of them, like Chief Mangosuthu Buthelezi, became the only person who was not at ease accepting this spurious independence. As a result of this, he made numerous attempts to dissuade other leaders to see eye to eye with him but his advice fell on deaf ears. Buthelezi's approach really became a vein attempt since in 1976, Transkei became independent under Kaizer Mathanzima, Bophuthatswana got its independence in 1977 under Lukas Nangope, followed by Venda in 1979 under Patrick Mphephu something that was a suicidal attempt according to Buthelezi, since all these people had to access South Africa through the use of a passport.

This surely happened against Chief Buthelezi's major attempts to warn people, especially in 1979, not to resort to this fake independence, but his attempts gathered no support. In 1979, through Inkatha, he issued 100000 pamphlets in Soweto and other townships on the Reef, urging blacks not to sell their birth right and stating that every black has a duty to remain South African by refusing to take out citizenship in 'independent homelands'¹⁰. Sadly,

²Fryer, *The Road to Democracy in South Africa, Volume- (1960-1970)*, 38.

³Pretorius, *A History of South African-from Distant Past to the Present Day*, 464.

⁴Pretorius, *A history of South African-from Distant Past to the Present Day*, 340.

⁵Fryer, *The Road to Democracy in South Africa, Volume (1960-1970)*, 41.

⁶Pretorius, *A History of South African-from Distant Past to the Present Day*, 340.

⁷Platzky, Walker: *The Surplus People-Forced Removals in South Africa*, 109.

⁸Baskin, *Striking Back-A History of Cosatu*, 328.

⁹Ross, *A Concise History of South Africa*, 145.

¹⁰Jeffery, *The Natal Story 16 Years of Conflict*, 23.

the myopic attitude that people had, prevailed since two years later pseudo independence was declared in Ciskei under Lennox Sebe in 1981. This then meant that more and more black people were leaving South Africa, something that meant that they were foreigners in their own land. This Chief Buthelezi's attitude remained so stern to such an extent that it gave him sour blood to some quarters as Botha's government began to mistrust him since he had warned people against homeland independence.

The Botha government did not trust Buthelezi. He spoke out strongly against the independence of the Zulu people, who comprised more than 20 % of the total population¹¹.

This was the greatest divergence of one man among many people like Chief Mathanzima, Lucas Mangope, and Lennox Sebe, who had viewed homelands as the biggest gain in their lifetime. The people of Transkei in 1976 lost their South African citizenship, something that was not given a thought, since their independence only gave them a political freedom without economic freedom. This purely showed the political myopia of the homeland-s leaders who could not think beyond their economic stability, as they forgot that their people wanted jobs more than anything else. Unfortunately, this was in line with what Verwoerd had planned by not allowing the development of industries in reserves because it would empower the homelands economically.

Economic self-sufficiency was never a viable or desired option. Verwoerd refused to permit industries to be developed within the reserves, which would risk the emergence of a stable and politically dangerous proletariat¹².

This was purely in line with what Chief Mangosuthu Buthelezi had warned people about, that they had to guard against becoming strangers in their own land. The obvious mistake that the leaders of the homelands did make was a failure realise that there was no industrial development in their homeland, so accepting independence was an economic suicide for the downtrodden people. The paradox was that- the people of these so-called independent homelands had to move people in droves to cities that were outside of their homelands with passports for the work opportunities, while their leaders were well at ease both politically and economically. ...the Bantustan strategy gave Bantustan administrators considerable worth, patronage and power¹³.

The Homelands and the Heavy Handedness of some of its Leaders

The establishment of the homelands naturally had to benefit both leaders and their people alike in terms of economic benefit as well as political rights. Surprisingly, the truth was the opposite since some leaders proved to be undemocratic from the outset to the point of being autocratic, something that led to heavy-handedness towards people. Leaders such as Kaiser Mathanzima of the Transkei, Chief Mangosuthu Buthelezi of KwaZulu and Lukas Mangope of Bophuthatswana soon developed a heavy-handed approach in their respective places, something that reversed apartheid attitude from apartheid leaders to black leaders of the homelands. Kaiser Mathanzima showed signs of political intolerance of any kind in the Transkei. In other words, he expected no political contestation or any form of resistance, as results those who attempted to do so-faced the iron hand of the person who was seemingly their messiah. The harassment and victimization of the higher order in the Transkei became an order of the day under Kaiser Mathanzima.

In addition to intimidation and harassment of the opposition, Matanzima (sic) used personal differences as a tool to silence those who differed with him. A case in point was the 1977 resignation of Stella Sigcawu as Minister of. It was believed that Matanzima (sic) forced her to resign after allegations that Chief Moshesh, another of his cabinet minister's cabinet her¹⁴.

This kind of political attitude that Mathanzima showed was the very attitude that the apartheid government was showing, not allowing people to express their views that differed from the government. This was the negativity that the homelands showed, something that revealed that all people are the same, in terms of wanting no rivalry at their disposal. Mathanzima had proved to be so keen on arresting and demoting more people, even those of notable positions, as he did to Chief Sabatha Dalindyebo, who was arrested and also suspended from his throne. After Dalindyebo's arrest, Matanzima (sic) suspended him as the paramount chief and replaced him with his brother Bambilanga¹⁵. This was the thing that the people of Transkei never expected from their seemingly political sympathizers. Economically, things in the Transkei stood to favour some and oppose others, as people of high political status and businesspeople immensely benefited in several ways from the economy of the homelands at the expense of the down-trodden masses. In addition to bureaucrats and politicians, a class of African traders and entrepreneurs also benefited from that Bantustan strategy...Loans and the grants set up local capitalists, and many also benefited from the departure of white traders from the homelands, giving the new African trading class a stake in the political order.

This whole situation showed that the establishment of homelands was only to benefit the few individuals, while the rest of the population was languishing in poverty of the highest order. In Bophuthatswana, Lukas Mangope also adopted very stern measures against anyone or anything that was seemingly suspicious under his reign. This made him even force women to carry passes, something that brought a lot of controversy in Bophuthatswana, as that homeland was politically duplicating South African practice. This became a very controversial situation as a result; some people of authority in Bophuthatswana like Chief Setlhoapile, openly disdained this authority as something unbecoming. Among the neighboring Barolong, in Genesa, Vryburg, Chief Setlhoapile declared himself opposed to passes and commanded women in his village to refuse the reference books¹⁶. This briefly showed that Bantustans were using procedures like those of apartheid South Africa. Surprisingly, Mangope put himself in line with the ethnically based injunction of ethnic separation, something that was referred to as ethnic cleansing, whereby he expelled all the non-Tswana people in Bophuthatswana. Under an ethnic-filled approach, he activated his police to harass and arrest all the non-Tswana people in Bophuthatswana, a thing that kept Bophuthatswana a place only for Tswana people. Bophuthatswana police began harassing non-Tswana in 1978 with the intention of removing them from Winterveld. Ndebele and Shangane people were advised to take out permits to remain there, but most refused. Winterveld plot owners

¹¹Pretorius, *A History of South African-from Distant Past to the Present Day*, 399.

¹²Worden, *The Making of Modern South Africa-Conquest, Segregation and Apartheid*, 111.

¹³Worden, *The Making of Modern South Africa-Conquest, Segregation and Apartheid*, 13.

¹⁴Theron, *The Road to Democracy in South Africa Volume 2 (1970-1980)*, 777.

¹⁵Theron, *The Road to Democracy in South Africa Volume 2 (1970-1980)*, 779.

¹⁶Lodge, *Black Politics in South Africa Since 1945*, 278.

(Tswana) attempted to shield squatters by legally harbouring them but were arrested in a pre-dawn raid along with the squatters¹⁷.

This, without doubt, became a severe measure that politically painted Bophuthatswana as *aterra non grata*, something that made people not see the difference between Bophuthatswana and South Africa. Furthermore, all the people who were against independence were severely dealt with, on the harshest terms. Andrew Lebakeng was among those who were against the independence of Bophuthatswana and because of this, he was arrested. His arrest in this case was purely based on the disrespect of Mangope, as he constantly besmirched Mangope's name in public. Lebakeng would stand a trial in 1983 for having violated the dignity of the President (Mangope) in 1979, by allegedly calling him a pig and a coward who was dressed as a woman¹⁸. These were the things that made people see independence of Bophuthatswana as a country of oppression rather than a country of freedom.

KwaZulu under Chief Mangosuthu Buthelezi also had innumerable cases that made KwaZulu a place of autocracy. In KwaZulu, as well as Chief Mangosuthu Buthelezi, who constantly rejected the notion of independence, but his Self-Governing Homeland had a similar character and attitude to independent homelands. He commanded a great deal of authority in all spheres of life, something that gave him indisputable hegemony in the whole of KwaZulu. This, therefore, meant that anyone who had a different political ideology or opinion from him was seen as a person who was his enemy to the point that he or she could be assassinated. There is a case in point where Mhlabunzima Maphumulo of Camperdown near Pietermaritzburg wanted to form a political party that would be called the Inala Party. His main aim with this Inala Party was to protect the dignity of King Goodwill Zulu that was fast losing his royalty. The point was that, in doing this, he was seen by Chief Buthelezi as one who had overstepped the political line in KwaZulu; he was there and then suspended from the post, and his chieftaincy was also suspended as well. He then became a victim in so many ways, something that led to multiple abuses. Unluckily, Chief Mhlabunzima Maphumulo, who was the President of the CONTRALESA, ended up assassinated and the basis of his assassination was suspiciously due to Chief Buthelezi's undemocratic nature of not wanting to see democracy being done in KwaZulu. Chief Buthelezi had suspiciously begun to use spies to gather any suspicious information that he thought might endanger his position in KwaZulu as the leader of the homeland. The point in case of this was in the Inkatha meeting, where Mhlabunzima addressed people freely and democratically against any form of discrimination against those who were non-Inkatha members, as he said:

I am an Inkatha man, but that does not mean that I must discriminate. I must accommodate every member of my tribe, irrespective of their political allegiance, be it UDF, COSATU, Inkatha or AZPO. I will not tolerate people who go from house to house, forcing others to join their organisations¹⁹.

In any normal society where, civil liberties are held in high regard, Chief Mhlabunzima Maphumulo's speech would have been tolerated, as in a democratic society, all people have freedom of speech, movement and choice. These were the words that resulted in Chief Maphumulo's death, a situation that left fingers pointing at Chief Buthelezi as the one who had orchestrated this death. Therefore, it is likely to become even clearer that Chief Buthelezi

was against anybody who could win people's popularity without him permitting that situation. The case of Barney Dladla became another case in point that stood to demonstrate this saga.

As an ex officio member of the KwaZulu legislative assembly, he joined Zulu King Goodwill Zwelithini and other in 1975 in forming Inala party in opposition to Chief Mangosuthu Buthelezi's Inkatha. Buthelezi used threatening tactics to force the Inala Party to dissolve, denouncing Maphumulo as someone bent on destroying Zulu unity²⁰.

Dladla was among those who were victimized because of his growing popularity. Dladla was one of the ministers in the KwaZulu Government who was a former unionist since he was an affiliate of the South African Congress of Trade Unions (SACTU). He was therefore highly targeted since he had become a threat in his leadership. The worst thing that Dladla did was to form a political party just three months after the formation of Inkatha. His political party became known as the Zulu Labour Party (ZLP), and it was seen as Inkatha's political opponent. This served to heighten Chief Buthelezi's suspicion about him becoming a political competitor.

The growing popularity of Dladla openly made him a *persona non grata* to Chief Buthelezi, who deserved nothing but his comeuppance. He therefore removed Dladla from the office altogether in an attempt of dealing with the pending competition. The growing popularity of Dladla and rumours of the impending formation of a new worker 'party led Buthelezi to change Dladla's portfolio to that of justice in June 1974 and to remove him from office altogether in August²¹.

This was the untold heavy handedness of Chief Buthelezi on people who acted out of his will because he did not believe in democracy. The main issue about Chief Buthelezi that so far has not been given proper attention, is that in 1990 he promulgated an Act that became known as the Amakhosi and Iziphakanyiswa Act of 1990. This Act had given him powers to appoint and dismissed chiefs as he deemed fit opposition in KwaZulu. This was the very Act that gave him overruling power to suspend Chiefs or dismiss them from their traditional positions. There is a case in point where he dismissed Chief Alphas Molefe of Nquthu, with whom Chief Buthelezi had been in loggerheads for some time. Chief Molefe ended up being dismissed by Chief Buthelezi in 1992 for his so-called political misbehavior. This political misbehavior was based on the fact that in August of 1989, he had gone to Zambia with other CONTRALESA members, something that, according to Chief Buthelezi was the sign of Chief Molefe having a connection with the African National Congress (ANC) that was in exile.

The suspension of Inkosi Elphas Molefe, of the Molefe clan in the Nquthu traditional authority, stems from three counts of alleged misconduct, including allegations that he acted "negligently or indolently" in discharging his duties. He is also charged with failing to resolve conflict and divisions within his traditional authority and failing to perform his duties in his traditional courthouse or office²².

In this regard, Chief Molefe's dismissal from his chieftaincy did not mean the end, as his people also suffered harshly in the hands of

¹⁷Theron, *The Road to Democracy in South Africa Volume 2 (1970-1980)*, 792.

¹⁸Theron, *The Road to Democracy in South Africa Volume 2 (1970-1980)*, 397.

¹⁹Moss, Obey, *South Africa Contemporary and Analysis*, 51.

²⁰<https://sahistory.org.za/people/mhlabunzima-joseph-maphumulo>

²¹Theron, *The Road to Democracy in South Africa Volume 2 (1970-1980)*, 271.

²²<https://iol.co.za/news/politics/2006-02-21-kzn-traditional-leader-suspended/>

Chief Buthelezi and Inkatha. Again, on the night of November 8, 1992, several homesteads that were within the jurisdiction of Chief Molefe's area that were brutally attacked by an armed group of men, leaving three people dead, including Chief Molefe's Induna (headman). Meshak Motlaung, who was Chief Molefe's oldest advisor was brutally assassinated; painfully, his case was covered up by KwaZulu Police (KZP), which was viewed as the paramilitary group for the KwaZulu government. In short, this was how people were victimized in the hands of the homeland's leaders under the homeland system in South Africa.

Homelands and the Forced Removals

The fact is that homelands in reality started in the 1970s, where they went into a full swing process, but it was predated by some homeland-related incidents, where people had to be forcefully removed due to homeland's demands like in the Transkei. In Matanzima's (sic) district, the scheme began to be implemented in 1962: it was intended that 2400 consolidated farming units would be produced, and people began to be removed from their land to make room for the showpiece irrigation scheme²³. In this case, homelands shared the common grounds with the forced removal in South Africa. Homelands in so many ways became the cause of resettlements in many so-called white areas, something that was technically part of the forced removals. The result was that, under homelands system, Blacks in particular became intolerable in many places that had been identified as white areas.

Enforcement of Section 10 of the Urban Areas Act became vicious and, to accommodate Africans evicted from white areas, whether from towns or farms, the government accelerated what is referred to as 'Bantu' towns and resettlement villages in the homelands. This situation became so critical in a way that it led to the forced removal of all Africans who had been misplaced by employment and other needs. In this situation, even the word or words 'Bantu towns' is apparently a misnomer and irresponsible since all towns had been reserved for white people and Africans were strictly confined to villages under the homelands system. The intricacy of homeland and removals grew in South Africa, a result of the intensification of Blacks removals in white areas, which became inevitable as it was driven by the following factors. The aged, the unfit, widows with dependent children, and families who do not qualify under the provisions of the Bantu (Urban Areas) Act No 25 of 1945 for accommodation in the European urban areas²⁴.

The intensification of this system, which was homelands-driven undoubtedly worsened the black people in any part of South Africa. The redrawing of the boundaries as a result of homelands system hugely led to the intensity of forced removals, something that swelled in some places to recognizable statistics. Between 1960 and 1980, according to official statistics, the population of the reserves increased from approximately 4.5 million to 11 million people (Simkins, 1983:54-6). Part of the increase was due to natural population growth; some of it was the result of redrawing boundaries so as to include some urban areas, notably KwaMashu and Umlazi outside Durban with a homeland; part of it was caused by insisting that new suburbs for blacks moving to cities be sited within a homeland²⁵. In some areas, like in a place that was formerly called Transvaal, as early as the 1970s, the Tsonga people of Gazankulu were found to be scattered to different places like Kangwane, Venda, Lebowa and Bophuthatswana. These people of Gazankulu could not

make a unified group. The apartheid government, in an attempt to form a new Bantustan or a homeland of Gazankulu, these people had to be removed from all the above-mentioned areas and put them in a single area to form a homogenous group of Gazankulu.

In 1970, 41% of Tsonga speakers lived in Gazankulu, while the rest lived in other Bantustans (namely Venda, Lebowa, Bophuthatswana, & Kangwane) or 'white' South Africa. Following constant removals in the 1970s, they managed to shift Tsongas into Gazankulu and 'foreigners' into neighbouring bantustans, bringing the percentage of Tsonga speakers living in Gazankulu to 43%²⁶.

This was another case in point where people had to be removed from their naturally preferred places to Gazankulu, in order to fulfil the homeland's requirements. Most of these people were against this removal because, to them, finding themselves forming a homogeneous group was totally less important. The case was that being adapted into a new geographical space meant less because they had to part ways with the environment in which they grew up. This kind of removal, to a certain extent, meant losing their livestock and farming land, things that had economically underpinned their livelihood. This effect of removing in response to resettlement patterns that were caused by the emergence of the 'black spot' became the order of the day in South Africa. This forcefully necessitated the move of many people from urban areas to newly emerged reserves. The overall effect of these measures was to massively enlarge the reserve population as various groups were excluded from the urban economy and forced back to reserves²⁷. This whole situation painted South Africa into black and white categories, something that directly responded to the creation of reserves or homelands in this country. The homelands or the reserves were reserved for Africans, as the word implies, who had to be removed from cities and farms despite the overcrowding thereof.

Africans evicted from farms were not allowed to move to cities. They had to go to the homelands, to the already overcrowded labour reserves. It is estimated that between 1950 and 1980 some 1.4 million people were squeezed off commercial farms and another 90000 were pushed off or migrated from towns other than eleven metropolitan areas in South Africa. Of these 1.4 million ended up in the reserves²⁸.

This was among the socio-economic intricacies that involved homeland-based removal, where people had to be pushed from pillar to post. This, in short, proved the eco-political intolerance caused by the establishment of homelands, which resulted in volumes of people being moved away from the cities, towns, and farms to homelands. Over a million labor tenants and farm squatters and 400000 city dwellers were resettled in Bantustans, the population of which increased by 70 per cent in the 60s. In addition, 327000 people were brought directly under the control of the Bantustan authorities as a result of townships being incorporated within the boundaries of the reserves neighboring them²⁹. This was the achievements that were scored by the homeland's system as it was intended by its designers.

²³Lodge, *Black Politics in South Africa Since 1945*, 284.

²⁴Platzky, Walker: *The Surplus People-forced Removals in South Africa*, 28.

²⁵Wilson, Ramphela: *Uprooting Poverty the South African challenge*, 38.

²⁶Platzky, Walker, *The Surplus People-Forced Removals in South Africa*, 125-126.

²⁷Lodge, *Black Politics in South Africa Since 1945*, 263.

²⁸Lodge, *Black Politics in South Africa Since 1945*, 263.

²⁹Lodge, *Black Politics in South Africa Since 1945*, 263.

The Dismantling of Homelands and Resistance from some Leaders

The post 1990 period rendered homelands dispensable since South Africa by then was heading for a unified South Africa, so all the fictitious institutions had been removed. The fact, therefore, was that dismantling homelands became an up struggle because its leaders were all in the eco-political comfort zone, something that made doing away with homelands a great loss. This openly shows that homelands have been made to benefit some and deprive others of their natural rights. In this way, the homelands had an open way for the coming of the democratic South Africa, and all those homelands' related benefits had to come to an abrupt end for all those who were entitled to them. The fact about the dismantling of the homelands is that, although homelands were against the incorporation into the new South Africa, there were only three that openly rose against it.

These were KwaZulu, Bophuthatswana, and Ciskei that went rebellious about being taken back to South Africa as part of South Africa again. The political climate in South Africa had shown that homelands had to be totally phased out owing to the ongoing political negotiations that ushered in the new political era. The leaders of these three homelands, Lucas Mangope for Bophuthatswana, Chief Mangosuthu Buthelezi for KwaZulu, and Oupa Gqozo for Ciskei, had shown reluctance to be part of the new political dispensation as it meant the dismantling of their homelands. On seeing the Mangope and Buthelezi resort to action, they believed that it would place them in a better position. Chief Buthelezi made some abortive attempts to try to form a Federal state of KwaZulu as a matter of getting KwaZulu under its political autonomy. He did this with a hope of enjoying a popular more especially among the white people, since he thought that the federal state might appear to be a better option than being under the pending African National Congress. Buthelezi, in his speeches, categorically warned the South African population, including Whites, about the pending pitfall of the one man one vote system. By saying this, he thought this would serve to entice the white population to what he was warning them about.

We will see great different statements by political parties and organisations in the coming pre-negotiations period. It is not whether parties are saying the right things about what they ought to be negotiating about what is important. ...If white South Africans want to succeed in establishing something other than a one-man-one-vote system of government in a unitary state, they will have to be more prepared to give and take than the National Parties now evidence of being prepared for. I guess that we will end up with one or another form of a federal system of government³⁰.

The white people, both provincially and nationally, on whom Chief Buthelezi had pinned his hope for a federal state, showed no inclination to be part of his plan. Sadly, this happened despite his immense efforts to mobilise them in terms of being part of his idea for the federal state. This made him quickly resort to another strategy of persuading some like-minded people like Lukas Mangope of Bophuthatswana and the right-wing Afrikaners, such as the Conservative Party and Afrikaans Volkunie, to form something that became known as the Concerned South African Group (COSAG). Unfortunately, this did not yield any good results, which showed that all his attempts were failing. The failure of his plans to be heeded nearly brought his political career to a screeching halt, a situation

from which he was saved by the Kenyan Professor Washington Okumu and Kissinger's team.

Okume played a very important part in diffusing the very charged atmosphere that nearly led to the outbreak of the civil war. The point then was to force and command all the recusant homeland leaders such as Chief Buthelezi, Oupa Gqozo and Lucas Mangope to relinquish power for the new coming order. This process became a key order of dismantling the homeland system and it can be said without doubt that it was an insurmountable part of dismantling the homelands system. As early as September of 1992, just three years after the release of the exiles, Ciskei under Gqozo was accosted for her to relinquish power for the new order. It is of utmost importance to say that this attempt became so horrendous since it was characterized by the death of many people, who had come to usurp power for Gqozo, as the whole process led to something that was called the Bisho massacre. The Bisho massacre was preceded by terrible threats that were made by the African National Congress (ANC), something that intensified the situation.

The ANC leaders bluntly warned: Brig Gqozo: Our people are coming to remove you from the seat of power. Come what may. When the following day came, Marchers reached the Ciskei border. A group led by Mr Ronnie Kasrils, a member of the NEC of the ANC and the central committee of the SACP, broke away and sprinted through the gap in the fence in the direction of Bisho. The Ciskei Defence Force opened fire when the group came within 100 metres of them³¹.

The Bisho massacre was seen and rated as the worst calamity in the pre-election period in South Africa. The point about this was that the process of freeing the country from the old order had reached the state of no return, something that made this massacre insignificant despite the number of people who died on that day. As a result, the struggle for liberating Ciskei went on unhindered. Bophuthatswana under Lukas Mangope also faced a similar situation, where his people wanted him to pave the way for a new order that was inevitable. Mangope, on seeing this, appealed to Constant Viljoen, whom he knew to be against the new pending order. Viljoen, as a mature soldier, assessed the situation and found out that his interference was unnecessary because there was also the paramilitary group for Eugen Terre Blanche, the AWB, which was so bloodthirsty.

Viljoen's moment of truth arrived when the ANC stirred up a rebellion in Bophuthatswana, which threatened to oust Mangope and his government in Mafikeng (now Mahikeng). Mangope asked urgently for Viljoen's assistance, but when Viljoen arrived, he realized he was in an impossible situation. He had not chosen the battlefield (to defend a homeland government), nor had he selected his allies (bloodthirsty AWB members who had rushed to Mafikeng to shoot black people)³².

The attack that was done on homelands definitely defined the moment of truth that heralded the democratic government in South Africa. Chief Buthelezi in KwaZulu was not an exception since he was also against the formation of the democratic South Africa.

Chief Buthelezi was unlike other homeland leaders as he had many supportive structures, ranging from KwaZulu Police (KZP), Inkatha Freedom Party, Caprivi trainees, and other subsidiary

³⁰Clarion Call- South Africa A New Government Plans for Action, 7-8.

³¹Jeffery, *The Natal Story of 16 Years of Conflict*, 369.

³²Pretorius, *A History of South African-from Distant Past to the Present Day*, 431.

Chief Buthelezi was unlike other homeland leaders as he had many supportive structures, ranging from KwaZulu Police (KZP), Inkatha Freedom Party, Caprivi trainees, and other subsidiary structures of different formations. This made approaching him require double efforts because these structures were his cornerstone of defense. The ANC members who had gathered political momentum after 1990 were more than prepared to dismantle all the apartheid structures, including the homelands system. These members took it upon themselves that the KwaZulu homelands were also dismantled to pave the way to democratic South Africa. They then made clear and discernible efforts to dismantle the KwaZulu homelands under recalcitrant Chief Buthelezi.

Huge numbers of the ANC supporters were bused in, and some members were said to be prepared to die if necessary. Mr. Raymond Suttner said that 'the moment of choice had arrived' for Mr. de Klerk and that if South African security forces interfered in the protest, there would be another massacre like Boipatong³³.

There were also other truth finding structures that were put in place to deal with the homeland's issues, such as the Goldstone Commission, Advocate Wallis committee and the Transitional Executive Council's task Group. These structures aimed at facilitating the transitional process by making sure that all that were stumbling blocks were removed. The Goldstone Commission was a special commission that was formed in 1992 as part of the fact-finding structure. This Goldstone Commission, as the name implied by the Hon Mr. Justice R. J Goldstone, who was assisted by two gentlemen, who were Mr. G. Steyn and Mr. S. Moshidi. Its main aim was to delve into all forms of injustices that had happened in the eighties and early nineties. Goldstone's investigation was to play a role in bringing to book some of the major practitioners of dirty tricks³⁴.

It is, however, important to say that although there were many culprits of the internecine violence of the 1990-1994 transitional period, this commission had its primary focus placed on the activities of KZP. This clearly showed that although this commission was said to be impartially designed, it never desisted from partiality as it placed its focus on the KZP, something that was about dismantling the homeland's structures and holding its leaders accountable for the injustices of the past. There were so many KZP-related injustices that were unearthed by this commission, something that proved that KZP was just a paramilitary entity that primarily worked for Inkatha and the KwaZulu government. In almost all areas under the control of the KZP, conflict monitors and lawyers have received reports and evidence of the involvement of the KZP. The role that the Goldstone commission played was to weaken the might of the KZP owing to the fact that their activities were being put under dire scrutiny.

Conclusion

Homelands were originally designed to alienate black people from white people, for the white people to maintain the highly regarded white supremacy in South Africa. Surprisingly, it also had its second subtle objective that was not given a thought even by black people, which was to alienate black people through ethnic division, as a matter of maintaining and promoting divide and rule. In short, this meant that homelands intended to promote enmity between Africans for them to mistrust one another to prevent and discourage any potential eco-political solidarity. Seemingly, this devious objective of homelands became clearer in the 80s and 90s, where there was a

black-on-black violence, more especially between the Zulu and the Xhosa speaking people, something that led to the unnecessary bloodshed in Gauteng in particular.

In this way, the world kept on blaming the violence on black-on-black animosity, forgetting that it was the very animosity that had been created by the homeland system through ethnic division/ in South Africa. Another objective of the homeland's system was to create an enclave of people, especially the homeland leaders, who were economically well-off, while millions and millions of grassroots people were languishing in abject poverty. This then served to create and confirm division with the same ethnic group, a thing that resulted in the heavy-handedness of some leaders in defense of their homelands induced eco-political privileges. The paradox was that those homeland leaders like Chief Mangosuthu Buthelezi, Kgosi Lucas Mangope and Chief Kaiser Mathazima became gatekeepers for apartheid. This became evident when it came to the dismantling of the homelands system, where some leaders like Chief Buthelezi, Kgosi Mangope, and Brigadier Gqozo defended the dismantling of the homelands system, something that resulted in a massive bloodshed in South Africa. Lastly, the homeland system was a perfect way of defending apartheid, as it was intended by the apartheid Nationalist leaders.

References

- Baskin, J. (1991). *Striking back the history of COSATU*. Braamfontein: Raven Press.
- Clarion Call- South Africa (2010). *A New Government Plans for Action*. KwaZulu-Natal.
- De Vos, A., Strijdom, H., & Fouche, C. (2011). *Research at grass roots: For the social sciences and human service professions*. Pretoria: Van Schaik Publishers.
- Fryer, D. (2004). *The road to democracy in South Africa, Volume 1(1960-1970)*. South Africa: Zebra Press.
- Jeffery, A. (2001). *The Natal Story: 16 Years of Conflict Published by the South African Institute of Race*. Braamfontein: Relations Auden House.
- Jeremy, Black, Baskin-Jonathan (1991). *Striking Black-A History of COSATU*. Braamfontein: Raven Press.
- Lodge, T. B. (1985). *Politics in South Africa*. Braamfontein: Raven Press.
- Minnaar, A. (1992). *Patterns of Violence: Case Studies of Conflict in Natal*. KwaZulu-Natal Human Science Research Council.
- Moss, G., & Obey, I. (1990). South Africa contemporary and analysis. *Journal of International Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jid.4010030114>.
- Platzky, L., & Walker, C. (2017). *The Surplus People-Forced Removals in South Africa*. Braamfontein: Raven Press.
- Pretorius, F. (2014). *A History of South African-from distant past to the present-day*. Pretoria: Protea Book House.
- Ross, R. (1999). *A Concise History of South Africa*. England: Cambridge University Press.
- Theron, B. (2006). *South Africa Democrat Education*. South Africa: UNISA.
- Theron, B. (2004). *The road to democracy in South Africa (Volume 2) (1960-1970)*. South Africa: Zebra Press.
- Welsh, D. (1971). *The roots of segregation: Native policy in colonial natal, 1845-1910*. Cape Town: Oxford University Press.
- Wilson, B. (1991). *A Time of Innocence*. South Africa: Random Century.
- Wodern, N. (1994). *The Making of South Africa: Conquest, Segregation and Apartheid*. USA: Cambridge.
- Websites
<https://www.biznews.com/thought-leaders/2023/09/18/andrew-kenny-on-mangosuthu-buthelezi>
<https://sahistory.org.za/people/mhlabunzima-joseph-maphumulo>

Received January 16, 2026

Revision received February 8, 2026

Accepted February 13, 2026

³³Jeffery, *The Natal Story of 16 Years of Conflict*, 269.

³⁴Welsh, *The Rise and Fall of Apartheid*, 419.

³⁵Minnaar, *Patterns of Violence Case Studies of Conflict in Natal*, 50-51.